

SHORTENED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Boltayeva Mekhrangiz Khaydarovna

SamSIFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8085921>

Abstract. Shortened words are abbreviations and contractions. Shortened phrases can be acronyms or initialisms. Symbols are used to represent words, concepts and units of measurement. This article describes shortened and their types of formation in English language.

Keywords: *shortened words, lexical shortening, clipping, blending.*

We know very well that words in English and Uzbek are formed using several methods. But not all the ways of forming words in these two languages are similar to each other. That is, the process of making them is carried out differently. If we look at the method of abbreviation, which is one of the methods of word formation in English and Uzbek languages, we can see some differences. Abbreviations are formed in the Uzbek language using the abbreviation method. The essence of this method is that certain parts of the noun compound are taken and joined together to form an abbreviated noun. For example: UN-United Nations Organization. In the Uzbek language, such abbreviations are found in the names of various organizations, institutions, as well as socio-political and scientific terms.

When forming a word by abbreviation, the abbreviation of the component of the compound has several different forms, the main forms are as follows:

- 1) Only the first letter of the compound letters is taken to form an abbreviation;
- 2) The initial part of the first word, taking the initial letter of the remaining word;
- 3) An abbreviated noun is formed from the main part of the compound components;
- 4) An abbreviated noun is formed from the first part of the word and the whole word.

If we consider the method of abbreviation in English, it means that abbreviations are abbreviated forms of a complete word. In this case, not only one word, but also groups of words can be abbreviations. Therefore, acronyms are shortened forms of words and groups of words. For example: Dr. – doctor, Oct. – October, M.P–Member of Parliament, S.O.S–Save our Souls. We can give many ways to make abbreviations in English.

Lexical shortening

Variants and expressions of abbreviations are also independent lexical units with a clear phonetic form and semantic structure. Some of them are expressed both orally and in writing. The rest are used only in the process of oral communication. For example: bus, mike, phone and trig, maths, sis etc.

Clipping

In this method, a new word is created by writing the first or more syllables in the words. But in many places, we find cases where the first syllable is written with the accent dropped. For example: sis-sister, Jap-Japanese, doc-doctor.

Traditional abbreviations are divided into several types depending on which part of the word they are shortened from:

- 1) Abbreviations shortened from the end of the word (called "apocope" in English): advertisement, lab-laboratory.
- 2) Abbreviations shortened from the beginning of the word (called "aphaeresis" in English): car-motor-car, phone-telephone
- 3) Abbreviations formed by omitting syllables of words or words between them (called "syncope" in English): maths-mathematics, pants-pantaloons, specs-spectacles.
- 4) Abbreviations shortened from the beginning and end of the word: flu-influenza, tec-detective, frig-refrigerator, etc.

A peculiar aspect of word contraction in modern English is that it often occurs in noun phrases. However, in very rare cases, we can see word shortening in adjective phrases related to slang. For example: ard-ardent, dilly-delightful, etc.

Blending

This method is a method in which parts of words are combined to form a new word - a new meaning. For example, let's take the word smog, this word is formed from the combination of two independent words. For example: smoke and fog (sm (oke+f) og) smog. We can find a similar example in another literature. That is, blending is a method of creating a new word as a result of combining two words. For example: clap+crash (cl (ap+cra) ash) clash, flash+blush(fl (ash+fl) ush) flush, slang+language((s+lang) language) slanguage. Shortening has a significant impact on the length of the word. With the help of punctuating short words, they are still understandable while retaining the meaning of what you are saying.

References:

1. Garner, Bryan, Garner's Modern American Usage. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press. 2009., p. 638.
2. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". - 2023. - T. 2. - №. 2. - C. 145-149.
3. Obidjonovna M. F. SOME TEACHING PRINCIPLES OF READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Archive of Conferences. - 2021. - T. 23. - №. 1. - C. 18-20.
4. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING FL //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor. - 2023. - T. 7. - №. 2. - C. 1.
5. Abdullayev A. A., Khalilova S. THE PART OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION //THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD. - 2023. - T. 2. - №. 4. - C. 60-65.
6. Lass R., The Cambridge History of the English Language, Cambridge University Press, 2006, Vol. 2, p. 36.